

**Cortical auditory evoked potentials in mild cognitive impairment: Evidence from a temporal-spatial
principal component analysis**

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Abstract

Mild cognitive impairment (MCI) is considered an intermediate transitional stage for the development of dementia, especially Alzheimer's disease (AD). The identification of neurophysiological biomarkers for MCI will allow improvement in detection and tracking the progression of cognitive impairment. Therefore, the primary objective of this study was to compare cortical auditory evoked potentials (CAEPs) between older adults with and without probable MCI to identify potential neurophysiological indicators of cognitive impairment. We applied a temporal-spatial principal component analysis (tsPCA) to the evoked potentials achieved during the processing of pure tones and speech sounds, to facilitate the separation of the components of the P1-N1-P2 complex. The probable MCI group showed a significant amplitude increase in a factor modelling N1b for speech sounds (Cohen's $d = .84$) and a decrease in a factor around the P2 time interval, especially for pure tones (Cohen's $d = 1.17$). Moreover, both factors showed a fair discrimination value between groups ($AUC = .698$ for N1b in speech condition; $AUC = .746$ for P2 in tone condition), with high sensitivity to detect MCI cases (86% and 91%, respectively). The results for N1b suggest that MCI participants may suffer from a deficit to inhibit irrelevant speech information and the decrease of P2 amplitude could be a signal of cholinergic hypoactivation. Therefore, both components could be proposed as early biomarkers of cognitive impairment.

KEYWORDS: Cortical Auditory Evoked Potentials; Principal Component Analysis; Mild Cognitive Impairment; Biomarker; P1-N1-P2 complex; T-complex

1. Introduction

As dementia prevalence is increasing, there is an urgent need to identify early biomarkers to detect and diagnose *mild cognitive impairment* (MCI) with the goal of preventing dementia such as *Alzheimer's disease* (AD). The MCI diagnostic entity, first described by Petersen et al. (1999), is considered to be a prodromal phase for dementia (Petersen, 2004). Individuals with MCI have a relatively high rate of progression to dementia (Petersen et al., 2009). Early identification and intervention before dementia onset is of crucial importance. Clinical criteria for MCI are not highly sensitive for diagnosis in early stages (Stothart, Kazanina, Näätänen, Haworth, & Tales, 2015). In this vein, research to find indicators or early markers of MCI is paramount.

There is a broad consensus that biomarkers are important in the diagnostic algorithm (Albert et al., 2011; Dubois et al., 2014; Petersen et al., 2009). Established diagnostic indicators of MCI and AD include cerebrospinal fluid biomarkers measured via extraction through a lumbar puncture such as *amyloid beta 1-42* ($A\beta_{1-42}$ the main compound of the senile plaques), *total-tau* (a marker for neuronal degeneration), and/or *phospho-tau* (a marker for hyperphosphorylation of tau protein and possibly for the formation of neurofibrillary tangles). Another diagnostic indicator is measurement of amyloidopathy with positron emission tomography (PET) imaging via amyloid tracers (Dubois et al., 2014). Structural brain imaging using magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and functional brain imaging using fluorodeoxyglucose (FDG) PET are considered as downstream topographical biomarkers for identifying structural abnormalities and atrophy (MRI) and cortical hypometabolism (FDG PET). These existing biomarkers are often invasive and all are costly (Blennow, Hampel, Weiner, & Zetterberg, 2010). Alternatively, neurophysiological biomarkers measured through electroencephalography (EEG), could prove to be a promising, inexpensive method for early detection and tracking disease progression. Specifically, EEG methods such as cortical auditory evoked potentials (CAEPs) might be particularly useful given relatively non-invasive and precise temporal measurements of neural activity.

In the adult brain, exogenous cortical neurophysiological responses to auditory stimulation, or *cortical auditory evoked potentials* (CAEPs), are obligatory responses that occur during the first 200 ms after the presentation of an auditory stimulus (Pratt, 2012). The most commonly examined exogenous CAEPs are the

P1, N1, and P2 waves, also referred to as the P1-N1-P2 complex. This complex reflects the transmission of information from the primary auditory cortex to association areas (Stothart & Kazanina, 2016).

The electrophysiological study of cognitive decline in older adults via CAEPs has most commonly utilized an auditory oddball paradigm, with response to infrequent stimuli (“oddball”) embedded in a series of more frequent stimuli (“standard”). Differences in exogenous CAEPs between adults with MCI or AD compared to cognitively normal older adults (CNOAs) have been found using this paradigm, pointing to abnormalities in the integrity of auditory information processing. These results suggest that CAEPs could index the presence of cognitive dysfunction (e.g., Gironell, García-Sánchez, Estévez-González, Boltes, & Kulisevsky, 2005; Golob, Irimajiri, & Starr, 2007; Golob, Johnson, & Starr, 2002; Golob & Starr, 2000; Golob et al., 2009; Lai, Lin, Liou, & Liu, 2010; Papaliagkas, Anogianakis, Tsolaki, Koliakos, & Kimiskidis, 2009; Papaliagkas, Kimiskidis, Tsolaki, & Anogianakis, 2008; Polich, Ladish, & Bloom, 1990).

Although the oddball paradigm is commonly used for eliciting exogenous CAEPs, these waves can also be passively elicited. In the oddball task, participants must actively use selective attention to distinguish between stimuli, involving higher-level cognitive processes that might affect the amplitude and latency of the obligatory waves (Hillyard, Hink, Schwent, & Picton, 1973). In addition, when working with cognitively impaired populations such as MCI or AD patients, the impact of their cognitive impairment on attention and resulting performance is unknown, likely fluctuating throughout the task and inconsistently impacting the elicited CAEPs. Thus, it is more desirable to avoid cognitively demanding tasks with these populations. This could also reduce participants’ stress, frustration, and/or non-cooperation.

Since the measurement of exogenous CAEPs does not require attention or behavioral responses, a passive paradigm may offer a purer measurement of obligatory CAEPs. As far as we know, just three studies have compared the P1-N1-P2 complex among individuals with MCI and CNOAs during a passive listening paradigm. Irimajiri, Golob, and Starr (2005) and Golob, Miranda, Johnson, and Starr (2001) showed results consistent with studies using active oddball tasks, such as larger P1 amplitudes for those with MCI relative to CNOAs, and no differences in N1 or P2, although the latter used a slightly different paradigm in which pure tone stimuli were presented in pairs. In contrast, Lister et al. (2016) used both pure tones (in a similar paradigm as used by Irimajiri et al., 2005) and speech sounds (syllable /ba/), and found no differences

between those with MCI and CNOA in P1 or N1. Instead, significantly smaller P2 amplitudes were obtained for participants with MCI than for CNOAs.

Lister et al. (2016) argued that the different pattern of results found between studies might stem from the different electrode montages used, i.e. the reference electrode and the location of recording electrodes (linked mastoids versus average reference and central electrodes versus the whole scalp). More specifically, only the use of an average reference allows for checking the reversal of field polarity that accompanies the P1-N1-P2 complex (Picton, Lins, & Scherg, 1995) and the choice of reference site can change the results from inferential statistics (see Dien, 1998, for illustration), making it difficult to compare across studies with these different methodologies. Further, different patterns of results are found depending on the paradigms, electrode configurations, and analysis procedures used.

Additionally, a crucial point neglected in previous research is that long-latency CAEPs are composed of different underlying sub-components, which can be difficult to disentangle with traditional analyses. For example, earlier literature on the N1 suggests that this wave is formed by at least three sub-components. The first is the N1b, a fronto-central negativity with cortical generators located in the superior temporal lobe (Näätänen & Picton, 1987; Vaughan & Ritter, 1970). Second, the “T-complex” is formed by two sub-components: The Ta component, a positive wave at approximately 100 ms, followed by the Tb component, a negative wave occurring at approximately 150 ms, also known as the N140 or N1c (Dien, Tucker, Potts, & Hartry-Speiser, 1997; Näätänen & Picton, 1987; Wolpaw & Penry, 1975). The T-complex is generated in secondary auditory cortex located in the superior temporal gyrus, and therefore largest at temporal electrodes (Tonquist-Uhlen, Ponton, Eggermont, Kwong, & Don, 2003). Finally, the vertex N1 or non-specific N1 (described by Näätänen & Picton, 1987) is a negative wave at approximately 100 ms, with maximum at vertex. The generator of this wave is not known and may not be specific to audition (Näätänen & Picton, 1987).

The objective of the current study was to decompose the average waveforms of obligatory CAEPs elicited in a passive paradigm as putative indicators of cognitive impairment, in an attempt to overcome some of the issues of previous studies. We used the same settings and paradigm as Lister et al. (2016) including both pure tones and speech sounds, and we submitted the CAEP data to a temporal-spatial principal component analysis (tsPCA), following a method developed by Dien (2012). PCA is a data driven method that

decomposes a CAEP waveform into its underlying components and is particularly useful in separating spatially and/or temporally overlapping components. Moreover, although changes in reference affect PCA component extraction, this approach is less susceptible to reference changes compared to more traditional CAEP measures (Kayser & Tenke, 2003).

2. Method

2.1. Participants

Cognitively normal older adult (CNOA) participants included those who contacted the University of South Florida (USF) Cognitive Aging Lab or Neurophysiology of Aging Lab regarding interest in participating in research. Additional participants with probable MCI were recruited by referral from the USF Suncoast Memory Clinic. A total of 42 participants composed the final sample, with an age range between 61 and 87 years. Of these 42 participants, 23 were from the group of 30 participants in Lister et al. (2016); seven participants from Lister et al. (2016) were not included in the current study because excessive noise in some electrodes to be included in the tsPCA¹.

All participants met the following inclusion criteria: 60 years and over, ability to speak, understand and read English; adequate hearing acuity, no greater than a moderate hearing loss (thresholds <70 decibels Hearing Level - dB HL) in the mid-frequency range (1 and 2 kHz); and Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA) scores ≥ 20 . The initial screening also ensured that participants had no history of stroke, transient ischemic attacks, head injury, Parkinson's disease, or other neurological disorders. Participants who were taking psychoactive or narcotic medications or medications for sleep promotion were excluded.

The MoCA, a particularly sensitive measure used to screen for MCI (Nasreddine et al., 2005), was used to categorize the 42 participants into two groups: CNOA (MoCA > 25; $n = 21$) or probable MCI (MoCA 20 – 25; $n = 21$). Prior to auditory ERPs testing, peripheral hearing was assessed using a standard comprehensive audiometric battery (see Lister et al., 2016 for a more detailed description). The group mean pure tone hearing thresholds for octave frequencies from 250 to 8000 Hz are provided in Supplementary material, Table S1.

The study protocol was approved by the Institutional Review Board of the University of South Florida and was in conformity with the principles embodied in the Declaration of Helsinki. Before data collection. All participants were informed about the study and signed the corresponding informed consent form.

2.2. Stimuli and procedure

A passive paradigm was used, consisting of two blocks of 300 standard stimuli each: a block of 1000 Hz pure tones and a block of the speech syllable /ba/ with a fundamental frequency of 200 Hz. Order of the two blocks was counterbalanced across participants. All participants were asked to watch the same close-captioned DVD episode of Scientific American Frontiers (Season 14 #1402) while ignoring incoming auditory stimuli. All stimuli were presented via E-Prime 2.0 (Psychology Software Tools, Inc.) at a calibrated level of 85 decibels Sound Pressure Level (dB SPL) via insert earphones (ER-3A by Etymotic Research). Duration of stimuli was 100 ms (5 ms rise/fall) and inter-stimulus intervals were 2.5 s for a total time of about 26 min.

2.3. Electroencephalographic recordings and signal pre-processing

The EEG recordings were completed in a dimly lit, sound attenuating booth. Continuous EEG activity was recorded from 64 sintered Ag/AgCl electrodes inserted in a cap (Compumedics Neuroscan EEG system) with SynAmps2 amplifiers, SCAN 4.5 Acquire software, at a sampling rate of 1000 Hz, and band-pass filtered from 0.1 to 100 Hz (12 dB/octave). The reference electrode was placed at vertex, and a high forehead electrode served as ground. Four electrodes, one on the outer canthus of each eye, and one on both the supra and infra orbital ridges of the left eye were used to monitor eye blink activity.

Offline analysis of the continuous EEG was performed using SCAN 4.5 Edit and BrainVision Analyzer 2.1 software. The analysis began with the application of a digital band-pass finite impulse response (FIR) filter between 0.1 and 30 Hz with a 12 dB/octave skirt, with zero phase shift. Ocular artifacts were corrected using a rolling average of 30 sweeps to compute linear transmission coefficients, followed by a point-by-point proportional subtraction, based on the averaged artifact in the trigger channel (SCAN 4.5 Edit). EEG epochs of 400 ms (-100 to 300 ms) were obtained, baseline corrected (-100 to 0 ms), re-referenced to an average reference, and averaged separately for each participant and stimulus type. Latency was negatively adjusted by the stimulus onset delay: 49 ms ($SD = 5.6$ ms) for the pure tone stimulus and 64 ms ($SD = 6.1$ ms) for the speech stimulus. Epochs containing artifacts greater than ± 100 μ v were automatically rejected from averaging, and all remaining epochs were individually inspected to identify those still showing artifacts (i.e. eye fluttering, lateral or slow eye movements, sweat and muscle artifacts, pulse or EKG artifacts). For each stimulus type, at least 50 artifact-free epochs were averaged (BrainVision Analyzer 2.1). The mean proportion of averaged trials in the speech condition for CNOA group was 253.05 ($SD = 75.95$) and for MCI group was

280.19 ($SD = 32.75$). In the tone condition the mean proportion of averaged trials for CNOA was 258.29 ($SD = 76.52$) and for MCI was 279.29 ($SD = 47.63$). No differences were found in the number of averaged trials between the groups in either the speech condition, $t_{(40)} = -1.50$; $p = .140$; or in the tone condition, $t_{(40)} = -1.07$; $p = .292$.

2.4. Data analysis

2.4.1. Traditional ERP Analysis

As in Lister et al. (2016), we performed a traditional, single-electrode analysis of the P1-N1-P2 complex. We repeated this analysis because the sample in Lister et al. (2016) was different from the current sample. Visual inspection of the grand averages revealed the P1-N1-P2 complex with maximum amplitude at FCz electrode. The averaged waveforms measured from FCz were used to determine the peak latencies and amplitudes of the P1-N1-P2 complex (see Figure 1). In addition, we also analyzed the T-complex at temporal electrodes, to have the whole data pattern from waves, which can be directly observed in this time range. T-complex was mainly composed by a positive peak (the Ta component) and a negative peak (the Tb component; see Figure 1). The averaged waveforms measured from T7 and T8 were used to determine Ta and Tb latencies and amplitudes. The selection of wave time-windows was based on observation of the mean ERP amplitudes ± 25 ms. Specifically, P1 was defined as the largest positivity occurring between 14 and 64 ms after pure tone onset and between 12 and 62 ms after speech onset. N1 was defined as the largest negativity occurring between 71 and 121 ms for both conditions. P2 was defined as the largest positivity occurring between 195 and 245 ms for pure tones and between 168 and 218 ms for speech. Due to common observed differences in latency between both hemispheres for the Ta and Tb components (Hämäläinen, Fosker, Szücs, & Goswami, 2011), different time intervals were defined in T7 and T8 electrodes. For T7, Ta was defined as the largest positivity between 71 and 121 ms for both conditions, and Tb as the largest negativity between 118 and 168 for the pure tones and between 170 and 220 ms for speech. For T8, Ta was measured as the largest positivity between 57 and 107 ms for both conditions and Tb as the largest negativity between 120 and 170 ms for the tone condition and between 109 and 159 for speech.

A robust ANOVA, denoted by “ $T_{WJ/c}$ ”, for each of the components was performed with type of stimulus (condition) as a within-subject factor with two levels (pure tones, speech) and the group as a between-subject factor, with two levels (CNOA, probable MCI), through the ERP PCA Toolkit version 2.54

(Dien, 2010a). The robust statistics function generates inferential statistical tests comparable to ANOVAs that are designed to be more robust against violations of statistical assumptions (see Dien, 2010a for a detailed description). In addition, effect sizes were calculated by means of Cohen's d for the group factor, interpreting the effect as small when $d = .2$, medium when $d = .5$, and large when $d = .8$.

Although the use of the MoCA cutoff to establish the diagnosis of probable MCI (20-25) is a common practice and the sensitivity and specificity of the test is high (Lonie, Tierney, & Ebmeir, 2009; Nasreddine et al., 2005), correlational analysis (Pearson or Spearman depending on the distribution) was carried out between the continuous MoCA scores and the amplitudes and latencies of each ERP deflection to ensure a relation between the MoCA scores and the waves. When significant correlations and differences between the groups based on the MoCA split were found, scatter plots were constructed to show the clustering.

In order to check the internal consistency of the CAEP measures, split half reliability analyses were performed for each group by computing correlations of the averages of odd trials and even trials, and corrected using the Spearman–Brown formula, when the differences between the groups were significant. In psychological measurement, a reliability from 0.7 is considered acceptable for research purposes (Furr, 2010). Correlational and reliability analyses were performed using the IBM SPSS Statistics package v.23 for Windows.

2.4.2. PCA analysis

In order to maximize the separation of the ERP components, the data were decomposed using a tsPCA for each stimulus type separately². The ERP PCA Toolkit version 2.54 (Dien, 2010a) was used to conduct this tsPCA. The initial selection of the number of factors to retain, both for the temporal and spatial steps, was based on a Parallel Test (Horn, 1965). The first step was a temporal PCA through Promax rotation, using the covariance matrix and Kaiser normalization for the loading weightings (see Dien, Beal, & Berg, 2005 for a detailed description of these procedures). This initial temporal PCA used the time points for each participant and electrode as variables, to extract linear combinations of time points to reduce the temporal dimensions of the original data set. Each temporal factor was then submitted to a spatial PCA using Infomax rotation (Independent Component Analysis; Dien, 2010b) to reduce the spatial dimensions of the data set, where recording sites were used as variables, and all participants and temporal factor scores were used as observations. Of note, just 58 of the 64 recorded electrodes were included in the tsPCA (M1/M2, CB1/CB2,

and AF3/AF4 were removed for excessive noise in most of the participants, i.e. the averages computed with these electrodes included less than 50 trials, taking into account the selected criteria for artifact rejection and the visual inspection of the epochs)³.

A special characteristic of the ERP PCA toolkit is that the portion of the original ERP data represented by each factor combination is reconstructed in a microvolt scale by multiplying the factor score by the corresponding factor loadings and standard deviations, facilitating the interpretation of the results. In this sense, it is possible to look for those factors that can be identifiable as ERP components or that present coherent topography in accordance with the temporal interval. In addition, in this study we used a criterion for factor selection as a reliable ERP component based on those factors that accounted for at least 1 % of unique variance. Finally, a robust ANOVA for each of the retained factors was performed with group as a between-subject factor with two levels (CNOA, probable MCI). As for traditional ERP analysis, effect sizes were calculated through Cohen's *d*. Moreover, and as for the traditional analysis, correlational analysis (Pearson or Spearman depending on the distribution) was carried out between the continuous MoCA scores and the factor amplitudes to ensure a relation between the MOCA scores and the factors. Again, when significant correlations and differences between the groups based on the MoCA split were found, the scatter plots were constructed to show the clustering. Correlational analyses were performed using the IBM SPSS Statistics package v.23 for Windows.

2.4.3. Receiver operating characteristics (ROC) analysis

Receiver operating characteristics (ROC) curves were calculated to obtain the classification rates (sensitivity and specificity) between CNOA and MCI of the CAEPs and PCA factors, when the group factor showed a main effect and the correlation between continuous MoCA scores and the CAEP or PCA parameters was significant. ROC curves were constructed by determining the sensitivity and specificity for a range of values of the significant variables. The area under the ROC curve (*AUC*) results were considered excellent for *AUC* values between .9-1, good for *AUC* values between .8-.9, fair for *AUC* values between .7-.8, poor for *AUC* values between .6-.7 and failed for *AUC* values between .5-.6 (Lüdemann, Grieger, Wurm, Wust, & Zimmer, 2006). The Youden's *J* Index was calculated for each value of the significant variables in order to obtain the best sensitivity/specificity balance.

ROC analyses were performed using the IBM SPSS Statistics package v.23 for Windows.

3. Results

Demographic characteristics for both groups are shown in Table 1. There were no significant differences between the groups in terms of age, $F(1,40) = 3.28, p = .078$, years of education, $F(1,40) = 1.13, p = .294$, or hearing in the left, $F(1,40) = .001, p = .977$ or in the right ear, $F(1,40) = .96, p = .333$. Chi-square analysis did not show significant differences between the groups in sex, $\chi^2 = 1.53, p = .217$ or race, $\chi^2 = 1.02, p = .311$.

3.1. Traditional CAEP results

The original grand averages in T7, T8 and FCz for both conditions and groups, prior to PCA, are displayed in Figure 1. Tables 2 and 3 provide the averaged peak amplitudes and latencies for P1, N1, P2, Ta, and Tb for both groups in each condition. In addition, Figure 2 shows overlaid CAEP single-plots of each participant in each group (A for CNOA; B for MCI), and in each condition overlapping both groups (C). The CAEP single-plots for each individual in each group, overlapping both conditions can be seen in Supplementary material, Figure S1 (CNOA) and Figure S2 (MCI).

As shown in Figure 1, the P1 wave was evident at fronto-central electrodes around 50 ms. The robust ANOVA for P1 amplitude did not show any significant main effects, group factor, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0, 35.4) = .09, p = .780, d = .12, 95\% \text{ CI} [-.49, .72]$; condition factor, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0, 35.2) = .46, p = .490$, or interaction, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0, 35.2) = 1.05, p = .300$. For P1 latency, no significant main effects were found for group factor, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0, 27.6) = .31, p = .570, d = .20, 95\% \text{ CI} [-.41, .81]$; or condition factor, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0, 35.5) = .57, p = .460$, but a significant interaction between condition and group was found, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0, 35.5) = 5.50, p = .027$. Although the follow-up two-way ANOVA comparing conditions for MCI group showed no significant differences, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0, 18.0) = 4.28, p = .060$, the latency was longer for pure tones (41.11 ms) than for speech (36.68 ms). The correlation with continuous MoCA scores was not significant for any of the P1 parameters in any of the conditions (P1 amplitude for speech: $r = .25; p = .110$; P1 amplitude for tone: $r_s = .11; p = .495$; P1 latency for speech: $r_s = .24; p = .127$; P1 latency for tone: $r_s = -.02; p = .904$).

A second wave, N1, was observed around 90 ms at fronto-central sites. The robust ANOVA showed a main effect of stimulus type for the amplitude of N1, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0, 35.9) = 13.36, p < .001$, with higher amplitudes for the tone condition (-4.13 μv) than for the speech condition (-3.64 μv). No differences were found for group factor, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0, 34.8) = .11, p = .750, d = .09, 95\% \text{ CI} [-.51, .70]$, or interaction, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0,$

35.9) = .13, $p = .710$. For N1 latency, although it was slightly earlier for pure tones (95.50 ms) than for the speech sounds (97.16 ms), the robust ANOVA did not show significance for the condition factor, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0,33.9) = 3.64$, $p = .055$. The group factor, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0,35.6) = .11$, $p = .740$, $d = .20$, 95 % CI [-.80, .41], and the interaction, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0,33.9) = 2.39$, $p = .140$, were not significant as well. No correlations between the continuous MoCA scores and the latency or amplitude of N1 were found in any of the conditions (N1 amplitude for speech: $r = .11$; $p = .480$; N1 amplitude for tone: $r_s = .07$; $p = .641$; N1 latency for speech: $r = .02$; $p = .918$; N1 latency for tone: $r = -.15$; $p = .355$).

The last wave at fronto-central electrodes was P2 with an approximate latency of 200 ms. Regarding the amplitude of P2, the robust ANOVA indicated no significant effects of condition, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0, 34.8) = 2.06$, $p = .150$, or the interaction, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0, 34.8) = .80$, $p = .380$. The factor group was also not significant, but the effect size was moderate, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0, 28.7) = 3.16$, $p = .090$, $d = .67$, 95 % CI [.03, 1.28]. Moreover, there was a significant correlation between the MoCA scores and the amplitude of P2 in tone condition ($r_s = .34$; $p = .026$), and although not significant between MoCA scores and the amplitude of P2 in speech condition, the effect was moderate ($r_s = .30$; $p = .054$). Regarding the reliability analyses for P2 amplitude in FCz, the Spearman-Brown coefficient for CNOA group in both conditions (tone and speech) was .97, for MCI was .94 for tone condition and .83 for speech condition. So, P2 amplitude was strongly reliable for both groups. The results for the latency of P2 indicated a significant main effect of condition, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0, 33.3) = 47.40$, $p < .001$, and also of the main group factor, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0,36.0) = 4.42$, $p = .041$, $d = .82$, 95 % CI [-1.44, -.18]. The latency of P2 was earlier for the speech sounds (197.68 ms) than for the pure tones (219.68 ms), and for the CNOA group (205.21 ms) than for MCI group (212.16 ms). The interaction between condition and group factors was not significant, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0, 33.3) = .28$, $p = .600$. A significant correlation between MoCA continuous scores and the latency of P2 in FCz in the speech condition was found ($r_s = -.34$; $p = .026$), but not in the tone condition ($r_s = -.21$; $p = .179$). The scatter plot for P2 latency in speech versus MoCA scores is displayed in Figure 3 (top). The Spearman-Brown coefficient for P2 latency was .94 in tone condition and .83 in speech for CNOA group, whereas for MCI group was .51 for tone condition and .69 in speech. The reliability of P2 latency for MCI group was not acceptable, mainly for tone condition.

Finally, we also analyzed the T-complex at temporal electrodes in both hemispheres. Two components were evident; a first positivity in both temporal electrodes at around 100 ms, the Ta component, and a

negativity at around 130 ms in T8 for both conditions and groups. At T7, the latency of the Tb had a clear peak at around 150 ms for the tone condition, but it was later, at around 180 ms for the speech condition. The robust ANOVA for the left hemisphere (T7) regarding the amplitude of the Ta component showed no significant differences between the conditions, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0, 33.2) = .00, p = .990$, or the interaction between condition and group, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0, 33.2) = .26, p = .620$. Although the group factor was not significant, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0, 36.0) = 3.07, p = .080$, the effect size was medium, $d = .72, 95\% \text{ CI } [.08, 1.33]$, being the amplitude for CNOA ($2.51 \mu\text{v}$) larger than for MCI ($1.91 \mu\text{v}$). No significant correlations between the MoCA scores and the amplitude of Ta were observed in the left hemisphere (Ta amplitude for speech: $r_s = .28; p = .073$; Ta amplitude for tone: $r = .26; p = .092$). The amplitude of Ta in the right hemisphere (T8) was significantly larger for the pure tones ($2.25 \mu\text{v}$) than for the speech sounds ($1.78 \mu\text{v}$), $T_{WJ/c}(1.0, 33.5) = 10.60, p = .003$. The group factor did not show significant differences, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0, 35.8) = 3.99, p = .052$, but the effect size was large, $d = .82, 95\% \text{ CI } [.18, 1.43]$, with larger amplitude for CNOA group ($2.39 \mu\text{v}$) than for MCI ($1.64 \mu\text{v}$). Moreover, the correlational analysis showed a significant correlation between the MoCA scores and the amplitude of Ta in T8, both for speech ($r_s = .43; p = .005$) and tone ($r_s = .38; p = .014$). The scatter plot for Ta amplitude in T8 in both conditions versus the MoCA scores is displayed in Figure 3 (bottom). Reliability analysis showed Spearman-Brown coefficient values for CNOA group of .96 and .88 for tone and speech respectively. For MCI group, the Spearman-Brown coefficient was .89 for tone and .90 for speech.

No differences were found for the latency of Ta in any of the electrodes (Ta latency in T7: condition factor, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0, 35.6) = .45, p = .510$; group factor, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0, 35.4) = 2.67, p = .120, d = .62, 95\% \text{ CI } [-1.23, .01]$; interaction, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0, 35.6) = .07, p = .790$; Ta latency in T8: condition factor, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0, 31.9) = 2.31, p = .140$; group factor, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0, 34.3) = .30, p = .600, d = .20, 95\% \text{ CI } [-.80, .41]$ interaction, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0, 31.9) = .31, p = .580$). No correlations were found between the MoCA scores and the latency of Ta in any of the electrodes (Ta latency for speech in T7: $r_s = -.28; p = .073$; Ta latency for tone in T7: $r = -.26; p = .096$; Ta latency for speech in T8: $r_s = -.12; p = .470$; Ta latency for tone in T8: $r = -.23; p = .143$).

Regarding the Tb component in T7, no main effects (condition factor, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0, 35.4) = 1.56, p = .210$; group factor, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0, 36.0) = 1.40, p = .250, d = .52, 95\% \text{ CI } [-1.12, .11]$; or interaction, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0, 35.4) = .25, p = .610$) were found for the amplitude. The robust ANOVA revealed a main effect of condition

for the latency, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0, 25.5) = 247.97, p < .001$, with longer latency for the speech (196.29 ms) than for the tone condition (150.84 ms), but no effects were found for group factor, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0, 35.4) = .11, p = .740, d = .12, 95\% \text{ CI} [-.49, .72]$ or the interaction, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0, 25.5) = 3.70, p = .060$. For the right hemisphere (T8), the amplitude of the Tb component was significantly larger, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0, 33.8) = 8.80, p = .007$, for the tone condition (-.92 μv) than for speech condition (-.41 μv). No amplitude differences were found between the groups, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0, 35.9) = 1.39, p = .240, d = .44, 95\% \text{ CI} [-1.05, .18]$, or the interaction between condition and group, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0, 33.8) = .11, p = .750$. Regarding latency, the robust ANOVA also displayed a main effect of condition, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0, 35.9) = 18.08, p \leq .001$, with longer latency for the tone (149 ms) than for the speech condition (138.11 ms). Again, the main factor group, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0, 36.0) = 1.17, p = .290, d = .44, 95\% \text{ CI} [-.18, 1.04]$, and the interaction, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0, 35.9) = .24, p = .640$, were not significant. The correlational analysis did not show any significant relationship between the continuous MoCA scores and the measures for Tb for any of the electrodes (Tb amplitude for speech in T7: $r = -.23; p = .142$; Tb amplitude for tone in T7: $r = -.21; p = .192$; Tb latency for speech in T7: $r = -.06; p = .704$; Tb latency for tone in T7: $r = .19; p = .238$; Tb amplitude for speech in T8: $r = -.05; p = .771$; Tb amplitude for tone in T8: $r = -.01; p = .940$; Tb latency for speech in T8: $r = .10; p = .516$; Tb latency for tone in T8: $r = .11; p = .487$).

3.2. PCA results

The waveforms and scalp topographies for each factor combination that met the criterion to be analyzed for each stimulus type are displayed in Figure 4. Each factor is labeled by its latency and the number of the spatial factor, along with the possible corresponding sub-component into brackets. All the factors extracted for each solution, the ones that met the criterion for being further analyzed and those which did not reach this criterion, are displayed in Table S2 in Supplementary material.

3.2.1. tsPCA solution for speech condition

The tsPCA for the speech condition generated a total of 15 factor combinations (5 temporal factors, each of them with 3 spatial factors) explaining 76 % of the variance. Nine factor combinations met the criterion for being further analyzed (see Figure 4, A)

F49 – One factor combination met the criterion for further analysis, **F49-SF1 (P1)**. This factor was a frontal positivity, with a widespread negativity over posterior and lateral regions, resembling P1. The robust ANOVA did not show significant differences between the groups, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0, 32.1) = .68, p = .420, d = .31, 95$

% CI [-.30, .91]. No significant correlation was found between MoCA scores and the amplitude of this factor ($r = .24$; $p = .128$).

F83 – Two spatial factors were retained. The first one, **F83-SF1 (N1b)** was a frontal negativity with polarity inversion over the temporal and posterior regions of the scalp, so as N1b. No significant differences between groups were found, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0,34.6) = .47$, $p = .500$, $d = .26$, 95 % CI [-.35, .86]. No significant correlation was found between MoCA scores and the amplitude of this factor as well ($r_s = .11$; $p = .503$).

The second spatial factor at this latency was a left temporal positivity, **F83-SF2 (left Ta)** resembling the topography of Ta for the left hemisphere. The robust ANOVA did not show a significant difference between groups, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0,35.7) = 3.87$, $p = .064$, but the effect size was medium, $d = .77$, 95 % CI [.13, 1.38], being the amplitude larger for CNOA (.59 μv) than for MCI group (.19 μv). However, no significant correlation was found between MoCA scores and the amplitude of this factor ($r_s = .19$; $p = .240$).

F115 – At 115 ms, two spatial factors were retained. The first of them, **F115-SF1 (N1b-2)**, was similar to **F83-SF1** frontal, with a maximum negativity around F1, and a positivity over temporal and posterior regions. The topography and timing of this factor resembled again the N1b component, especially for the MCI group. Actually, the robust ANOVA showed a significant difference between groups, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0,35.0) = 5.09$, $p = .030$, $d = .84$, 95 % CI [.19, 1.45], with larger amplitude for MCI (-1.56 μv) than for CNOA (-.74 μv). The correlation between the amplitude of this factor and the continuous MoCA score was significant, showing a positive relation, $r = .37$, $p = .017$ (Figure 5, top).

The second spatial factor at this time interval, **F115-SF2 (left Ta-2)** was a left temporal positivity, similar to the second spatial factor for **F83-SF2 (left Ta)**, resembling again the topography of Ta. No significant differences were observed between the groups, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0,35.6) = .76$, $p = .390$, $d = .33$, 95 % CI [-.29, .93]. No significant correlation was found between MoCA scores and the amplitude of this factor ($r_s = .06$; $p = .728$).

F186 – One spatial factor was further analyzed, **F186-SF1 (P2)**. This factor clearly resembled P2, a positivity with a fronto-central distribution (FCz), but explained very little variance. The robust ANOVA did not show a significant effect between the groups, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0,35.1) = 3.90$, $p = .060$. However, the effect size was medium, $d = .77$, 95 % CI [.13, 1.39], being the amplitude slightly larger for CNOA (.78 μv) than for

MCI (.38 μv). In addition, the correlation between the factor amplitude and the MoCA scores was significant ($r_s = .35, p = .024$).

F195 – This last factor for speech condition was related to three spatial factors. The first one, **F195-SF1 (P2-2)** modeled a big fronto-central positivity with polarity inversion in occipital electrodes. This seems therefore a factor extracting again the P2 as factor **F186-SF1**, but explaining much more variance. As F186, the ANOVA did not show a significant effect, $T_{WJ}/c(1.0,34.3) = 2.91, p = .100$, but a medium effect size was found, $d = .64, 95\% \text{ CI } [.01, 1.25]$, with larger amplitude for CNOA (2.71 μv) than for MCI (1.94 μv). This split into two factors for the same wave might be explained by latency jitter among the participants mainly in CNOA group in this time interval, as can be seen in the single plot for speech (Figure 2) and in the separated analyses for groups in speech (data not shown), having the CNOA group two factors around this interval (191 ms and 207 ms). The correlation between the amplitude of this factor and the continuous MoCA scores was also significant ($r = .39, p = .011$).

The second spatial factor was a left temporal negativity corresponding with the Tb wave of the T-complex, **F195-SF2 (left Tb)**. The robust statistics showed no differences between the groups, $T_{WJ}/c(1.0,34.8) = .01, p = .910, d = .05, 95\% \text{ CI } [-.56, .65]$. No significant correlation was found between MoCA scores and the amplitude of this factor ($r = -.04; p = .817$).

The third and last factor, **F195-SF3 (sustained positivity)** was a right temporal positivity matching with the sustained positivity observed after the Tb component in T8 in the grand averages. No differences were found between the groups, $T_{WJ}/c(1.0,31.8) = .11, p = .740, d = .14, 95\% \text{ CI } [-.47, .74]$. No significant correlation was found between MoCA scores and the amplitude of this factor ($r_s = -.03; p = .846$).

3.2.2. tsPCA solution for tone condition

The tsPCA for tone condition generated as well a total of 15 factor combinations (5 temporal factors, each of them with 3 spatial factors) explaining 74 % of the variance. Seven factor combinations met the criterion for being analyzed (see Figure 4, B)

F51 – One factor combination met the criterion for further analysis, **F51-SF1 (P1)**, with the same topography and timing as P1. The robust statistics showed no differences between the groups, $T_{WJ}/c(1.0,35.9) = .10, p = .760, d = .11, 95\% \text{ CI } [-.49, .72]$. No significant correlation was found between MoCA scores and the amplitude of this factor ($r = .18; p = .243$).

F91 – For this peak, three spatial factors met the criterion for being further analyzed. The first one, **F91-SF1 (N1b)** was a widespread frontal negativity with polarity inversion over the temporal and posterior regions of the scalp. The timing and topography of this peak correspond to the N1b component. No significant effects were found between the groups, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0,36.0) = .62, p = .440, d = .30, 95\% \text{ CI} [-.32, .90]$. No significant correlation was found between MoCA scores and the amplitude of this factor ($r_s = .07; p = .682$).

The second spatial factor at this latency, **F91-SF2 (left Ta)** was a left temporal positivity, therefore Ta for the left side. The robust ANOVA did not show any significant difference between the groups, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0,33.8) = 2.61, p = .120$. Although the effect size was medium, $d = .62, 95\% \text{ CI} [-.01, 1.23]$, no significant correlation was found between MoCA scores and the amplitude of this factor ($r_s = .18; p = .261$).

The last spatial factor at this latency, **F91-SF3 (right Ta)**, was a temporal positivity with maximum at T8, resembling the Ta wave in the right hemisphere. No significant effects were observed between groups, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0,35.7) = .46, p = .510, d = .26, 95\% \text{ CI} [-.35, .87]$. No significant correlation was found between MoCA scores and the amplitude of this factor ($r = .16; p = .313$).

F134 – One spatial factor was retained, **F134-SF1 (left Tb)**. This factor was a posterior temporal negativity with maximum amplitude in T5/P7, resembling Tb in the left hemisphere. Although, slightly larger for CNOA group, the differences were not significant, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0,35.0) = 1.17, p = .290, d = .40, 95\% \text{ CI} [-1.0, .22]$. No significant correlation was found between MoCA scores and the amplitude of this factor ($r = -.13; p = .425$).

F183 – At 183 ms, one spatial factor was further analyzed, **F183-SF1 (P2)**. This factor clearly resembled P2, a positivity with fronto-central distribution. The robust ANOVA showed significant differences, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0,33.1) = 10.42, p = .0032$, and a large effect size, $d = 1.17, 95\% \text{ CI} [.50, 1.80]$, being the amplitude larger for CNOA ($2.18 \mu\text{v}$) than for MCI ($.91 \mu\text{v}$). The correlational analysis showed a significant relationship between the amplitude of the factor and the MoCA scores, $r = .46, p = .002$ (Figure 5, bottom).

F260 – The last factor for tone condition, with a latency of 260 ms was related to one spatial factor, **F260-SF1 (lateP2/early P3a)**. This factor modeled a fronto-central positivity, in accordance with a late P2 or an early P3a. The robust statistics did not show differences between groups, $T_{WJ/c}(1.0,28.6) = 2.13, p = .160, d = .57, 95\% \text{ CI} [-.06, 1.17]$. No significant correlation was found between MoCA scores and the amplitude of this factor ($r_s = .19; p = .211$).

3.3. Receiver operating characteristics (ROC) analysis results

We constructed ROC curves for the variables which showed differences between groups and a significant correlation between continuous MoCA scores and CAEPs or PCA parameters (Figure 6): P2 latency in speech condition, Ta amplitude on the right hemisphere in both conditions, F115-SF1 (N1b-2) in speech solution and F183-SF1 (P2) in the tone solution. The ROC curve for P2 latency in speech condition showed an *AUC* of .704 (95 % CI [.54, .86], $p = .024$) with the best classification rate showed a sensitivity of 91 % and a specificity of 52 %. The ROC curve for Ta amplitude at T8 showed an *AUC* of .728 (95 % CI [.57, .89], $p = .011$), with the best sensitivity and specificity values of 76 % and 81 %, respectively. For the speech solution, F115-SF1 (N1b-2) reached an *AUC* of .698 (95 % CI [.54, .86], $p = .028$) with the best sensitivity and specificity values of 86 % and 43 %, respectively; and for the tone solution, the *AUC* for F183-SF1 (P2) was .746 (95 % CI [.59, .89], $p = .006$) with the best sensitivity and specificity values of 91 % and 52 %, respectively

4. Discussion

Our prior work examined whether CAEPs could be possible early indicators of MCI (Lister et al., 2016). In these follow-up analyses, we have furthered our study of CAEPs in MCI by means of a more detailed analysis. Specifically, we performed a tsPCA on the P1-N1-P2 complex recorded from a sample of older adults with and without probable MCI during a passive hearing paradigm using two types of stimuli, pure tones and speech sounds. PCA allows the identification of covariance patterns among EEG measurements, and so it is useful to separate superimposed ERP components, even if they overlap (Dien et al., 1997). This procedure is therefore appropriate to study the P1-N1-P2 complex, given the superimposition among different components in this time range. This kind of separation analysis allowed us to draw clearer conclusions about group effects on the different components. In sum, our current results point out differences in the pattern of neural auditory processing between probable MCI and CNOA participants, suggesting that the N1b for speech sounds and the P2, especially for pure tone stimuli, might be useful indicators for MCI.

In agreement with the previous results by Lister et al. (2016), both the traditional analyses and tsPCA solutions revealed no amplitude differences between the groups for P1. Although in the present study we did not find significant differences between the groups in the N1 and P2 amplitude analyzed through traditional, single-electrode amplitude analysis, differences in the tsPCAs were found. Specifically, we found larger

amplitudes for MCI than for CNOA in one factor extracted in the speech analysis resembling the N1b component, and the factors extracted from both tsPCAs resembling the temporal pattern and topography of P2 showed larger amplitude for CNOA than for MCI, but just significant for the tone solution. The pattern of results for P1 and P2, however, is at odds with the few existing studies in the field, showing in general an over-responsivity of these components in MCI participants compared to CNOA.

In this vein, larger P1 amplitudes for MCI than for CNOAs have previously been reported mostly during active paradigms (Golob et al., 2007, 2002; Golob & Starr, 2000) and in only one truly passive task (Irimajiri et al., 2005). Interestingly, the same result was also reported for healthy older adults when compared to young participants (Alain, McDonald, & Van Roon 2012; Lister, Maxfield, Pitt, & Gonzalez, 2011; Ross, Schneider, Snyder, & Alain, 2010). Nevertheless, Bidelman, Lowther, Tak, and Alain (2017) did not find differences for P1 between MCI and CNOA participants in an active forced-choice task using speech stimuli, and Buchwald, Erwin, Read, Van Lancker, and Cummings (1989) reported a complete absence of P1 in AD patients during a passive binaural hearing design. P1, also termed as P50, is considered the earliest component of the long-latency CAEPs, but it is also the same component as the Pb from the middle-latency CAEPs (Yvert, Crouzeix, Bertrand, Seither-Preisler, & Pantev, 2001), just recorded in a different temporal basis. It typically peaks between 40 and 70 ms and is generated bilaterally in the primary auditory cortex (Korzyukov et al., 2007; Liegeois-Chauvel, Musolino, Badier, Marquis, & Chauvel, 1994), reflecting the regulation of sensory information from the peripheral nervous system to the cortex. However, a multiplicity of components is observed around this time interval. Some authors have established that P1 is composed by different sub-components, Pb1 and Pb2, peaking around 50 ms and 70 ms respectively, formed the so-called Pb complex (Yvert et al., 2001). All the different peaks around this interval might reflect distinct neurobiological processes having distinct anatomical locations (Korzyukov et al. 2007). Thus, it is possible that the differences observed among the studies in the amplitude of P1 in both CNOA and MCI are due to the selection of different peaks with similar amplitude, given the broad time window in which researchers have searched for the P1.

One of the main strengths of tsPCA is that it offers a procedure free of peak selection, by searching for covariance patterns to separate the constituent components of the ERP waveform (Dien, 2012). Our tsPCA solutions showed just one factor in each solution, **F49-SF1 (P1)** in speech solution and **F51-SF1 (P1)** in tone

solution, around the time interval of P1, with maximum amplitude at frontal locations, showing the same amplitude across the groups. This factor would be compatible with the so-called Pb1 component. Other spatial factors extracted at this time seem to model the Pa1, but did not reach the criteria for being analyzed (see Table S2 in Supplementary material). In addition, although Bidelman et al. (2017) explained their lack of effect on P1 amplitude in MCI by the use of speech stimuli instead of tones, we have not found P1 amplitude differences between pure tones and speech sounds. Therefore, at least for one of the components of P1, Pb1, individuals with MCI did not show any over-responsivity.

The results for N1 and P2 in MCI/AD literature have been less consistent than for P1, with some studies showing amplitude increases (Bidelman et al., 2017; Polich et al., 1990), whereas others did not find any significant difference (Golob et al., 2001, 2009; Irimajiri et al., 2005). The same inconsistency of results has been found for healthy older adults when compared to young people (see Alain, Roye, & Salloum, 2014).

During the time interval of N1 several peaks can take place, proposing N1 as a multifactorial wave (Näätänen & Picton, 1987). The different tsPCAs performed here revealed peaks at 83 ms and 115 ms for speech solution and at 91 for tone solution, with three different topographical factors resembling N1b and the Ta component of the T-complex in the right and in the left hemispheres. The tsPCA for speech revealed two factors, **F83-SF1** and **F115-SF1** with the same topography, but the second modelling N1b with significant larger amplitude for MCI participants, although present in both groups, and a positive correlation with MoCA scores, so indicating more positive amplitude values are related to higher MoCA scores. Therefore, N1b might suffer from some latency jitter across the participants in the speech condition, modelling two factors.

Moreover, the separated analysis for each group (data not shown) in this condition revealed a N1b at 89 ms for CNOA, whereas the N1b factor for MCI was at 105 ms. Although both factors were larger for MCI, just the second one reached significance. The ROC curve computed for this factor showed fair discrimination values, with 86% sensitivity. So, the over-responsivity of N1 showed by Bidelman et al. (2017) for the speech stimuli is somewhat confirmed in the present study. On the other hand, the tsPCA for the tone condition revealed just one factor consistent with N1b (**F91-SF1**), without differences between groups. The larger amplitude for N1b in MCI participants for speech stimuli may be due to the greater salience of this type of sounds (Woods, 1995). In addition, some studies have found an age-related increase in the N1 amplitude in

response to task-irrelevant auditory stimuli that participants were instructed to ignore, suggesting a deficit to inhibit the attention to non-relevant stimuli (Alain and Woods, 1990; Alain, McDonald, & Van Roon, 2012).

Unlike in our previous work (Lister et al., 2016), here the T-complex was analyzed through traditional peak measurement at T7/T8 electrodes. The tsPCAs solutions extracted different factors resembling Ta and Tb components. As far as we know, the components underlying this complex have not been previously studied in participants with MCI, and minimally among CNOA (Horváth, Gaál, & Volosin, 2017), making it difficult to draw any conclusions.

The traditional analysis for Ta revealed larger amplitudes for CNOA than for MCI in both hemispheres, with moderate to large effect sizes. The reliability of the Ta amplitude in T8 was highly acceptable (values around .90) for both conditions and groups. In addition, a moderate and positive correlation between MoCA scores and Ta amplitude in T8 was observed for both conditions, indicating the higher the MoCA score the higher the amplitude of Ta in T8. In fact, Ta amplitude on the right hemisphere showed a moderate value to discriminate between MCI and CNOA individuals, with good specificity values.

Surprisingly, no differences between the groups were found for the factors corresponding to this component in any of the PCA solutions, and the effect sizes were moderate for the left Ta in both analyses, but small for the right Ta. As for N1b, the tsPCA for the speech solution showed two factors modelling this component in TP8 (**F83-SF3** and **F115-SF3**). Although these factors did not reach the criterion for being further analyzed, and the analysis did not show differences between the groups (see Table S2 in Supplementary material), **F83-SF3** resemble Ta in the right side for both groups, whereas **F115-SF3** resemble Ta in the right side mainly for CNOA. The pattern of the tsPCA solution for speech in the left hemisphere followed a similar pattern than in the right, with two factors, the later one (**F115-SF2**) representing mainly the CNOA group. Of note, the amplitude for this factor was slightly larger for CNOA than for MCI, although not significant, and in the separated solutions for each group (data not shown) a factor at 142 ms was observed for CNOA group, whereas no similar factor was found for MCI. These results are possible due to latency jitter across the participants, since the variability both for CNOA and MCI in speech condition was really high. In the case of MCI group this variability in the latency of Ta is much evident (see Figure 2, B) with different peaks from 50 ms onwards, both for speech and tone conditions. Thus, it is possible that the Ta component observed and measured in the raw ERP was not a unique sub-component, but a product of some overlay

among these different peaks occurring around this temporal interval, and therefore its discrimination properties should be taken cautiously.

For Tb, no group effect was found in the traditional analysis, and the tsPCAs revealed several factors resembling the topography of this component at 186 and 195 ms for speech, and at 134 ms and 183 ms for tone, but showing no differences between the groups. It is important to point out the high variability observed from 140 ms onwards in the single-plots and the amount of factors modelling both negativities and positivities around this time interval (Table S2), suggesting this component was not homogeneous between conditions and groups.

The T-complex seems to be generated in the secondary auditory cortex, providing a measure of higher-level auditory function (Cacace, Dowman, & Wolpaw, 1988; Tonnquist-Uhlen et al., 2003), and some studies propose it to be especially involved in speech perception (Tonnquist-Uhlen et al., 2003), somewhat in accordance with the Ta results for the speech sounds found here. However, given the latency jitter observed for this component in the present study and the scarcity of studies investigating the T-complex in the context of the aging process and cognitive deterioration, all the results found in the present study should be replicated and further investigated.

The last wave to be analyzed in the present study was P2. Although, unlike the previous study of Lister et al. (2016), here differences between the groups in the amplitude of P2 measured through traditional peak amplitude were not found, the effect size was moderate and the correlation between the continuous MoCA score and the amplitude of P2 in tone was also moderate and positive. In the same way, as we established above, our tsPCAs solutions revealed a P2 amplitude difference between MCI and CNOA groups. Probable MCI participants showed significant smaller amplitude for the factor modeling P2 at 183 ms in the tone solution, **F183-SF1 (P2)**, with a large effect size and fair discrimination values between groups. The sensitivity value was high, allowing a correct MCI detection rate of 91 %. Nevertheless, the specificity values were poor (52 %) probably indicating some abnormal values of this marker in CNOA individuals as well. In fact, the tsPCA for speech solution showed two factors modelling the P2 wave, one at 195 ms and another at 186 ms, both larger for CNOA than for MCI with quite large effect sizes, although not reaching significance. This result seems again due to latency jitter across participants in the speech solution, especially for CNOA, somehow blurring the amplitude differences between the groups in this condition.

The dearth of studies investigating obligatory CAEPs in MCI have shown conflicting results regarding P2. Bidelman et al. (2017) found larger N1-P2 amplitudes in MCI than in CNOAs in an active task using speech stimuli. However, in the present study we found larger N1b amplitude for MCI participants than for CNOA in accordance with Bidelman's results, but a decrease in P2 amplitude. There are several methodological differences between the Bidelman et al. (2017) study and the current study that could be contributing to the differences in findings. First of all, they just used speech stimuli, and the present differences in P2 were especially related to pure tone stimuli; the differences in their study seemed to be age-dependent, with oldest participants showing no such amplitude increase. It is important to indicate that in the study of Bidelman et al. (2017) the participants ranged in age from 52 to 86 years, a broad range that makes comparisons difficult, since brain changes are expected to be very different from middle adulthood (52 years old) to oldest-old adults (86 years). In addition, they had a very small sample, with only eight participants with MCI. We used thresholds of <70 dB HL in the mid-frequency range (1 and 2 kHz) to ensure audibility of stimuli while they used thresholds of ≤ 25 dB HL based on pure-tone average thresholds (i.e., average of 500, 1000, 2000 Hz). Different inter-stimulus intervals were also used across the studies, with 2.5 s used in the current study and they used an inter-stimulus interval between 400 – 600 ms that jittered randomly in 20 ms steps. This latter difference in particular may have played a role in the finding of opposite results because auditory evoked responses are known to be sensitive to inter-stimulus interval manipulation. However, most of studies have not found any difference in P2 amplitude between older adults with and without MCI (Golob et al., 2007, 2002, 2001; Irimajiri et al., 2005).

Moreover, and unlike our previous results, the traditional analysis revealed longer P2 latency for MCI than for CNOA group. The reported effects of age on the P2 latency have been more consistent than for the amplitude, with most studies reporting an age-related increase in P2 latency (see Alain et al., 2014). This delayed P2 for MCI participants has also been found in the visual modality (Fix, Arruda, Andrasik, Beach, & Groom, 2015). Nevertheless, the reliability of P2 latency for participants with MCI in the present study was not acceptable and a significant correlation with MoCA scores was found for speech condition, but not for tone stimuli. This pattern of results for P2 latency, is probably due to the presence of two real peaks in the temporal interval selected to measure P2, one of them mainly present in the tone condition, especially for MCI group, and still observable in the grand averages.

In this line, this second peak was also modelled by a factor at 260 ms in the tone solution, not present in the speech solution. This later factor resembled the topography of P2, so this could be a 'late-P2', due to latency jitter across participants. However, given the relatively long presentation intervals and loud tones used in the present study, it is more probable that this factor at this late latency is modelling an early P3a, reflecting an involuntary attention capture towards the sounds, mainly in MCI. However, no group effects were observed for this factor. Therefore, we can conclude that the direct measure of P2 in the single waveforms was not accurate given the existence of these two peaks and thus, P2 latency cannot be proposed as a valid biomarker for MCI, at least with the results found in the present study.

Taking into account all the results observed in the present study, we might have two potential good biomarkers for MCI, the larger amplitude of N1b for speech sounds and the smaller amplitude of P2 for pure tones. The over-responsivity of N1b for MCI participants may be due to a deficit to inhibit irrelevant information and disengage the attention resources from non-significant stimulation, suggesting a problem in attentional control.

On the other hand, and according to several authors, P2 reflects, apart from the input to temporal cortex, auditory driven output of the mesencephalic reticular activating system (RAS; see Crowley & Colrain, 2004; Näätänen & Picton, 1987). The most important component in this system consists of a cholinergic reticulothalamic pathway that facilitates the activation of corticopetal relay neurons in the thalamus (Mesulam, 1995). Therefore, it seems that the two most likely generators of P2 are locations strongly dependent of the cholinergic system, i.e. temporal cortex and RAS. The decreased P2 amplitude in participants with probable MCI found in the present study might be related to an early cholinergic hypofunction, commonly associated to the progressing memory deficits with aging (Haense et al., 2012; Schliebes & Arendt, 2011).

A diagnostic instrument based on the study of N1b and P2 in a passive auditory task using speech and pure tones as stimuli, both through traditional analyses, taking the peak amplitude of the components individually, along with tsPCA analysis, could be an inexpensive and easy instrument useful as a coadjuvant tool for neuropsychological diagnosis in the early detection of cognitive impairment. In addition, the study of the cholinergic hypofunction in MCI patients through other type of EEG analysis, as the study of the resting-state EEG would be really useful and easy, since some studies have found that the occipital alpha rhythms

reflect the impairment of cholinergic neuromodulation from basal forebrain to thalamus and/or occipital cortex (Babiloni et al., 2015). In this vein, Babiloni et al. (2009) have shown that the occipital sources of alpha rhythms in amnesic MCI participants are abnormal in association with the impairment of the cholinergic connections to cerebral cortex.

Therefore, we propose an instrument based on neuropsychological assessment, analyses of resting-state EEG rhythms and analyses of N1 and P2 waves in a passive auditory task with speech and pure tone stimuli, could be useful to the early detection of the disease and to track the progression of the impairment and the conversion to dementia.

There are, however, certain limitations of the present study. One of the weaknesses of the tsPCA technique is its sensitivity to latency jitter (see Möcks, 1986), due to latency shifts across participants, and/or conditions, resulting in extra factors. In this study we tried to overcome this issue computing the tsPCA for both conditions separately, but latency jitter across participants seemed to be present as well, displaying extra factors modeling latency differences for N1b, Ta and P2, especially related to the speech condition. We were able to recognize this issue because we used a high-density montage (i.e. 64 channels) making it possible to detect the same topography in these factors. A related limitation of tsPCA is that this technique does not allow the study of latency patterns across the factors as they are defined in terms of a fixed time course (Dien, 2012). So, we cannot compare the factors on a time basis, and we have to, instead, analyze the peak latency in the traditional ERP waveform. As we can see with our results for P2 latency, the commonly method used to measure the peak of a single wave, i.e. define an interval taking into account the grand averages, is not appropriate since different overlapping peaks can contribute to the latency differences, making the results invalid. So, we propose to measure peak latencies individually for each participant to obtain a reliable measure.

Several considerations should be taken into account in future studies. The different criteria used to diagnose MCI, such as screening tools as MoCA, more complex criteria as Petersen's algorithm, or the presence of imaging biomarkers, as established by the International Working Group (IWG-2 criteria; Dubois et al., 2014), and the type of MCI studied, i.e. amnesic or not amnesic/single or multi-domain, should be considered when making comparisons, since very different prevalence of MCI and results can be obtained. In this vein, Golob et al. (2007) showed that the increase in P1 amplitude was significant when compared to

controls just for those with multi-domain MCI and not for those with single-domain MCI. Another aspect that must be controlled for is the hearing sensitivity of the participants. Those studies that have found CAEP over-responsivity did not assess hearing among the participants (Golob et al., 2007, 2002; Golob & Starr, 2000) or just in some participants but not in all of them (Irimajiri et al., 2005). Thorough hearing assessment is imperative when studying auditory evoked responses, given evidence that of enhanced auditory CAEPs among those with hearing loss as compared to those with normal hearing for physically identical sounds (Alain et al., 2014; Harkrider, Plyler, & Hedrick, 2006).

In summary, our results suggest that the amplitude of N1b and P2 of the obligatory CAEPs measured through a passive auditory paradigm with both speech and tone stimuli, can indicate those participants with probable MCI. We propose these waves as candidates for early biomarkers of cognitive impairment to be further investigated. The use of tsPCA provides a suitable tool to separate obligatory CAEPs and obtain a purer measure of the auditory cortical potentials during the time interval between 50 and 300 ms.

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Authors Notes

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Data Availability Statement

The datasets (ERP and PCA data) supporting the results and conclusions of this manuscript are available at Figshare (<https://figshare.com>): <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.8969648.v1>

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Footnotes

¹ In Lister et al.'s (2016) study just FCz was analyzed, whereas in the present study 58 electrodes were included in the tsPCA to obtain reliable results (see Dien et al., 2012 for a complete explanation). As a rule of thumb it is not recommended to interpolate more than 10% of the total number of the electrodes (6 in our case) to maintain the integrity of the data. Therefore, we decided to exclude from the analyses those participants with more than 6 noisy electrodes (apart from M1/M2, CB1/CB2, AF3/AF4, see below note 3) in order to avoid problems with the ICA procedure implemented for the spatial rotation in the PCA.

² A tsPCA including both types of stimuli as within-subject variable was also performed, generating a total of 20 factor combinations (5 temporal factors, each of them with 4 spatial factors) explaining 80% of the variance. However, the results for this solution are not presented here since the primary focus of the present study is to find biomarkers capable of differentiating between CNOA and MCI participants, and not to compare both conditions. In addition, given some difficulties with the understanding of the mixed PCA analysis due to latency jitter between the conditions, the separated analysis for each stimulus type allows us to increase the interpretability of the solutions.

³ In general, the waveforms contained many artifacts. Therefore, taking into account the rule of interpolating a maximum of 6 electrodes, and to maintain the same number of channels in all the participants, we excluded M1/M2, CB1/CB2 and AF3/AF4 instead of interpolating them because the preservation of other electrodes was more relevant for the study of CAEPs. Moreover, electrodes at the border of the array, as M1/M2 and CB1/CB2, should not be interpolated since enough neighbors were missing.

Table 1*Demographic characteristics of participants*

Group	MoCA score	Age	Years of education	% White	% Female	PTA in dB HL	
						Left ear	Right ear
CNOA	27.86 (1.32)	70.78 (5.36)	15.43 (2.68)	100%	62%	24.14 (10.11)	22.14 (10.97)
p-MCI	22.90 (1.99)	73.89 (5.74)	14.52 (2.84)	95 %	43%	24.05 (11.41)	25.52 (11.37)

Note. CNOA = Cognitively Normal Older Adults, p-MCI = probable Mild Cognitive Impairment, MoCA = Montreal Cognitive Assessment, PTA = pure tone average

Table 2*CAEPs mean (SD) amplitude (μ v) and mean (SD) latency (ms) for pure tones*

Group	P1		N1		P2		Ta-T7		Ta-T8		Tb-T7		Tb-T8	
	Amplitude	Latency	Amplitude	Latency	Amplitude	Latency	Amplitude	Latency	Amplitude	Latency	Amplitude	Latency	Amplitude	Latency
CNOA	1.21 (.76)	39.26 (6.69)	-4.08 (1.14)	94.47 (5.95)	2.97 (1.44)	217.05 (14.44)	2.47 (.97)	97.68 (6.79)	2.67 (1.12)	88.84 (8.91)	-1.80 (1.22)	154.11 (8.94)	-1.03 (.78)	151.37 (10.67)
p-MCI	1.20 (.62)	41.11 (8.13)	-4.18 (1.14)	96.53 (5.82)	2.03 (.74)	222.32 (14.92)	1.94 (1.20)	101.37 (6.07)	1.83 (1.08)	92.11 (14.07)	-1.22 (1.07)	147.58 (10.55)	-0.80 (.91)	146.74 (10.32)

Note. CNOA = Cognitively Normal Older Adults, p-MCI = probable Mild Cognitive Impairment

Table 3*CAEPs mean (SD) amplitude (μ v) and mean (SD) latency (ms) for speech sounds*

Group	P1		N1		P2		Ta-T7		Ta-T8		Tb-T7		Tb-T8	
	Amplitude	Latency	Amplitude	Latency	Amplitude	Latency	Amplitude	Latency	Amplitude	Latency	Amplitude	Latency	Amplitude	Latency
CNOA	1.23 (.71)	41.53 (5.22)	-3.55 (1.40)	97.47 (7.21)	3.06 (1.49)	193.37 (11.30)	2.55 (.99)	96.68 (7.87)	2.12 (.90)	87.21 (11.40)	-1.48 (1.19)	194.00 (10.23)	-0.58 (.76)	139.16 (11.26)
p-MCI	1.09 (.67)	36.68 (11.19)	-3.74 (1.08)	96.84 (5.49)	2.41 (1.10)	202.00 (7.23)	1.87 (.84)	100.95 (7.46)	1.45 (.92)	88.58 (12.20)	-1.08 (1.15)	198.58 (14.08)	-0.23 (.75)	137.05 (11.37)

Note. CNOA = Cognitively Normal Older Adults, p-MCI = probable Mild Cognitive Impairment

Figures

Figure 1. Grand averaged CAEP waveforms measured from FCz and temporal electrodes (T7/T8) for pure tones (left) and speech sounds (right) stimuli, and for both groups, CNOA (black line) and probable MCI (red lines). Abbreviations: CNOA = Cognitive Normal Older Adults; MCI = Mild Cognitive Impairment.

Figure 2. CAEPs single-plots overlaid for, A) each participant in the CNOA group in each condition in the three analyzed electrodes (T7, FCz, T8); B) each participant in the MCI group in each condition in the three analyzed electrodes (T7, FCz, T8); C) each participant in both groups for each condition. Abbreviations: CNOA = Cognitive Normal Older Adults; p-MCI = probable Mild Cognitive Impairment.

Figure 3. Top: Scatter plot of P2 latency in FCz for speech condition versus MoCA scores; Bottom: Scatter plot of Ta amplitude in T8 for both speech condition (circles) and pure-tones (squares) versus MoCA scores. Vertical line indicates demarcation of the two groups: Symbols to the left indicates data for probable mild cognitive impairment; symbols to the right indicate data for cognitive normal older adults

Figure 4. Waveforms and scalp topographies of the nine factors retained in the temporal-spatial PCA for speech sounds (A) and of the seven factors retained in the temporal-spatial PCA for pure tones (B), for both groups, CNOA (black lines) and probable MCI (red lines). Note the different scales used across factors.

Abbreviations: CNOA = Cognitive Normal Older Adults; p-MCI = probable Mild Cognitive Impairment.

Figure 5. Top: Scatter plot of F115-SF1 (N1b-2) amplitude in F1 for speech condition versus MoCA scores; Bottom: Scatter plot of F183-SF1 (P2) amplitude in FCz for tone condition versus MoCA scores. Vertical line indicates demarcation of the two groups: Symbols to the left indicates data for probable mild cognitive impairment; symbols to the right indicate data for cognitive normal older adults

Figure 6. ROC curves between CNOA and p-MCI for the variables when the group factor showed a main effect and the correlation between continuous MoCA scores and the CAEP or PCA parameters was significant: P2 latency in speech in FCz; Ta amplitude in both conditions in T8; F115-SF1 (N1b-2) in speech in F1; and F183-SF1 (P2) in tone condition in FCz. Abbreviations: CNOA = Cognitive Normal Older Adults; p-MCI = probable Mild Cognitive Impairment.

